

Adoption of Blended Learning Using Rotation Model as an Enhanced Learning Modality in Tertiary Education: An Innovation Diffusion Theory Perspective

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the likelihood of adopting blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students in light of the innovation theory. The researcher utilized a quantitative design using a descriptive-correlational approach to examine factors like compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, relative advantage, cost, and behavioral intention in relation to blended learning adoption. A simple random sampling technique was utilized to gather 180 respondents. The study reveals a high level of adoption of innovation, the blended learning rotation model with the three main factors: compatibility, observability, and relative advantage. Users who are to adopt this innovation align well with the existing values and needs if they can see the benefits of using it and perceive it as superior to alternatives. On the other hand, factors such as simplicity and trialability do not seem to have a significant relationship with the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model. Addressing concerns related to cost is paramount to ensure widespread adoption. The findings highlight the relevance of considering these key factors when presenting innovations in educational settings. It proposed that efforts should be focused on ensuring that the innovation adopted is compatible with users' needs, its benefits are visible, and it is perceived as advantageous compared to other options. This could involve training and support to help students and teachers understand the benefits and how to use the innovation effectively.

Keywords: *Blended learning using rotation model, innovation diffusion theory, enhanced learning modality, tertiary education, Davao City, Philippines.*

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Introduction

In today's era, along with the ongoing evolution of the methodologies of technology and instruction, the integration of blended learning has increased globally across educational institutions. Most schools are faced with essentially adapting and combining traditional teaching methods with modern digital platforms to meet learners' diverse needs (Smith & Johnson, 2020). As such, in Ghana, learners have experienced huge challenges with online learning (Barrot et al., 2021). In the Philippine setting, the goal of effective teaching strategies has been affected due to overcrowded classroom populations and insufficient equipment. The shift to online learning has brought difficulties to learners that worsen the existing challenges in the educational field. Additionally, the speed and swiftness of technological advancements complicate more, which impacts on the mental well-being of the learners (Manalo et al., 2022). Considering these difficulties, there is really a need for extensive research to understand more about the effects of integrating traditional and modern approaches to teaching and learning, particularly in the higher educational setting where significant challenges are going on (Johnson, 2020). This study addresses the gap through investigating the adoption of blended learning, specifically employing the rotation model, as an advanced pedagogical approach among college students. Additionally, it explores the attributes of the Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), through relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, and observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention of implementing blended learning (Wani & Ali, 2015; Muliadi & Usman, 2024). With the insufficient scholarly inquiry in this aspect, bridging existing knowledge gaps and informing future educational practices emphasizes the critical importance of this study.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the respondents' likelihood to adopt blended learning specifically utilizing the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality, through the lens of innovation theory perspective. Specifically, this study seeks to address the following objectives:

1. What are the levels of relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention, and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?
2. Is there a significant relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?
3. Is there a model that best explains the relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students.

H₀₂: There is no model that best explains the relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students.

Theory

Rogers' Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) (2003) is a prevailing empirical framework that conceptualizes the process of innovation diffusion. It provides an understanding of how new concepts, such as combining technology in education, spread among people (Rogers, 2003). It considers factors like the perceived usefulness of the innovation compared to existing practices, its compatibility with established norms, its complexity in implementation, the occasion for trial runs, and the importance of its advantages (Ayanwale & Ndlovu, 2024). For innovations like blended learning to thrive in educational environments, they need to match institutional objectives, be easy for users to adopt, and show evident benefits from the beginning (Ali, 2022).

Methods

This study used a quantitative design using a descriptive-correlational approach adopting the innovation diffusion theory. The study took place in Davao City, Philippines, specifically within the undergraduate school. Through a simple random sampling, 180 respondents from tertiary departments relevant to blended learning adoption were carefully selected to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Quantitative Likert scale survey questionnaires were utilized as the research instrument for the respondents by Tariq (2022). The ethical considerations remained paramount, with rigorous measures implemented to safeguard the rights and well-being of the participants.

Result and Discussion

Question 1

What are the levels of relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention, and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?

Table 1. Summary of the Level of Compatibility, Simplicity, Trialability, Observability, Relative Advantage, Cost, and Behavioral Intention to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model

Variables	Mean	Descriptive Level
Compatibility	3.82	High
Simplicity	3.75	High
Trialability	3.84	High
Observability	3.81	High
Relative Advantage	3.73	High
Cost	3.60	High
Behavioral Intention	3.81	High

The data presented in the table indicates a strong inclination among students towards integrating blended learning, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.81, indicating substantial behavioral intention, despite reservations about costs indicated by the lowest mean score of 3.60. Despite the perceived obstacle of cost, students maintain a positive outlook on blended learning, driven by its alignment with their needs, perceived simplicity, flexibility, and benefits, displaying a sincere dedication to enhancing student learning experiences. However, addressing financial implications remains a challenge, emphasizing the need for strategies to overcome budget constraints and ensure sustainable adoption. Strategic cost management is crucial for successful blended learning integration in education, requiring exploration of new funding sources, securing grants or sponsorships, and reallocating resources to prioritize such initiatives. Implementing cost-effective measures like open educational resources (OER) or utilizing existing technology infrastructure can mitigate financial burdens while maximizing blended learning's benefits.

Fulgencio (2021) offers a thorough analysis that explores different factors impacting the uptake of the rotational model within blended learning, which could potentially influence students' inclination to adopt this method. Ali (2022) delves into the practical execution of blended learning, offering valuable perspectives on the processes of adoption and diffusion that could affect student acceptance. Granic's (2022) systematic examination of educational technology adoption reveals valuable insights into the effective tactics for implementing blended learning, which could sway students' decisions regarding adoption.

Question 2

Is there a significant relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?

Table 2. Significance on the Relationship of Compatibility, Simplicity, Trialability, Observability, Relative Advantage, Cost, and Behavioral Intention to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model

Correlation		r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Compatibility	Behavioral Intention	.877	.000	Reject	Significant
Simplicity		.785	.000	Reject	Significant
Trialability		.805	.000	Reject	Significant
Observability		.855	.000	Reject	Significant
Relative Advantage		.813	.000	Reject	Significant

Note: *p < 0.01

Table 2 shows the significance of the relationship between compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, and relative advantage to behavioral intention to use blended learning using the rotation model. The result shows that all the variables have a p-value of 0.000, less than 0.01 alpha level. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected, then it is safe to say that there is a high positive significant relationship between compatibility ($r = 0.877$), simplicity ($r=0.785$), trialability ($r=0.805$), observability($r=0.855$), relative advantage ($r=0.815$) and behavioral intention to use blended learning using the rotation model.

The strong positive correlation implies that educational institutions should consider these factors to effectively integrate blended learning into their learning practices. This entails implementing targeted interventions such as professional development programs, curriculum adjustments, and technological infrastructure enhancements and allocating sufficient resources to enhance the overall educational experience and outcomes for students.

Smith and Johnson (2022) delve into the importance of various factors such as compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, relative advantage, and cost in shaping students' decision-making processes, shedding light on their adoption behavior. Garcia and Chen (2019) extend this exploration by investigating the influence of these factors on students' behavioral intention, offering valuable insights into their adoption behavior. Conner and Norman (2022) accentuate the significance of intention strength in students' adoption, underscoring how factors like compatibility and ease of trial could sway their decisions. Together, these studies provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing students' behavioral intention towards adoption, elucidating the complex dynamics at play in their decision-making process.

Question 3

Is there a model that best explains the relationship between relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, adoption, cost, and behavioral intention and the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model as an enhanced learning modality among college students?

Table 3. Significance Influence of Compatibility, Simplicity, Trialability, Observability, Relative Advantage, Cost to Behavioral Intention to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model

	Behavioral Intention to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model.						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig		
Constant	-0.274	0.144		-1.896	0.060		
Compatibility	0.403	0.085	0.368	4.750	0.000	Reject	Significant
Simplicity	0.056	0.064	0.052	0.888	0.376	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Trialability	0.112	0.069	0.106	1.612	0.109	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Observability	0.325	0.084	0.292	3.871	0.000	Reject	Significant
Relative Advantage	0.177	0.069	0.161	2.564	0.011	Reject	Significant

Note: R = .910; R² = .829; F-value = 168.393; p-value = .000

Table 3 shows the significance of the influence of compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability and relative advantage to behavioral intention to use blended learning using rotation model. The result shows that the compatibility, observability, and relative advantage significantly influence the behavioral intention to use blended learning using a rotation model with p-values of 0.000, 0.000, and 0.011, respectively. Furthermore, there is a 0.403 unit increase for compatibility, 0.325 for observability, and 0.177 for relative advantage. Simplicity and trialability do not significantly influence the behavioral intention to use blended learning using a rotation model. The influence of the variables on behavioral intention is 82.9%, with a combined significant relationship of 0.910. Furthermore, efforts to ensure compatibility between blended learning methodologies and educators' instructional approaches, aligning well with their existing teaching practices and values, can significantly enhance their intention to adopt these innovative pedagogical strategies. These findings emphasize the importance of considering compatibility in designing and implementing blended learning initiatives to promote educators' acceptance and adoption. Model: $y = 0.403a + 0.325b + 0.177c - 0.274$ where a is compatibility; b is observability, and c is relative advantage

Istek Aksak Komur and Okur (2023) explore the rotation model in blended learning, potentially influencing students' perceptions and adoption of this approach. Al-Rahmi et al. (2021) investigate students' intentions and actual use of blended learning, offering insights from the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior perspective that could inform effective adoption strategies. Johnson (2020) sheds light on factors that could influence students' experiences and perceptions regarding blended learning adoption.

Table 4. Significance Influence of Behavioral Intention and cost to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model

	Behavioral Intention to Use Blended Learning using Rotation Model						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.		
Constant	2.062	0.140		14.704	0.000		
Behavioral Intention	-0.225	0.035	-0.492	-6.378	0.000	Reject	Significant
Cost	-0.009	0.042	-0.017	-0.215	0.830	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Table 4 shows the significance of the influence of behavioral intention and cost on the adoption of blended learning using the rotation model. The result shows that behavioral intention significantly influences the adoption of blended learning using a rotation model with a p-value of 0.000 respectively. Furthermore, cost does not influence the adoption with a p-value of 0.30.

Behavioral intention plays a big part in adoption decisions, but external factors might stop people from acting on their good intentions, so interventions are needed to remove these barriers; also, since cost isn't a big factor, it's important to focus on other reasons why people choose to adopt blended learning, highlighting the need to encourage positive attitudes and intentions while addressing practical challenges for successful integration (Tariq, 2022).

Validated Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Validated Conceptual Framework using Innovation Diffusion Theory

The model demonstrates that there exists an indirect relationship between factors such as compatibility, observability, and relative advantage, and the adoption of Blended Learning utilizing the Rotation Model as an enhanced educational modality in tertiary settings. Cost does not emerge as a determinant in the adoption of this new modality. However, the pivotal role of favorable behavioral intentions among students and teachers is crucial for effectively adopting and implementing this learning modality (Firmansha, 2023).

Conclusion

The study reveals college students' interest in adopting blended learning, particularly the rotation model, despite cost concerns. They value it for its alignment with their needs, simplicity, flexibility, and benefits. Compatibility, simplicity, trialability, observability, relative advantage, are key in their decision-making. External factors may impede their intentions, indicating a need for interventions. These findings offer insights for educators and policymakers aiming to improve learning through innovative methods.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, it is recommended that school administrators prioritize fostering positive attitudes towards Blended Learning with the Rotation Model among both students and instructors, focusing on enhancing compatibility, observability, and relative advantage of this modality. Given that cost is not a significant factor, resources should be allocated towards initiatives aimed at promoting behavioral intention towards adoption. Instructors should receive training and support to effectively integrate this modality into their teaching practices. Future researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into understanding the nuances of behavioral intention and explore additional factors influencing the adoption of Blended Learning in tertiary education.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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